

The influence of the amount of recycled material on microstructure and properties of recycled single-domain YBCO bulks

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ABSTRACT

Novel recycling process based on chemical dissolution was employed to grow REBCO bulks; recycled material obtained by recycling defective YBCO single-domain bulks was added (15 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 45 wt.%) to raw materials to prepare recycled precursor powder. Subsequently, single-domain YBCO bulks were produced using TSMG. Single-domain bulk recycling was chosen, as it represents the most challenging form of waste in the context of REBCO superconductor production. The properties and microstructure of recycled bulks were analyzed in detail. Single-domain YBCO bulks were grown successfully from the recycled precursor powder. Furthermore, it was found that their properties could be tuned by varying the amount of the added recycled powder. This work has demonstrated that up to 30 wt.% of recycled material can be seamlessly incorporated into existing REBCO production processes with only minimal impact and is that even more recycled material can be incorporated as the process matures and scales up.

1. Introduction

High-temperature Superconductors (HTS), characterized by their ability to exhibit superconductivity at comparatively higher temperatures, have revolutionized numerous technological domains due to their unique properties [1–4]. Among the various HTS materials, Rare-earth Barium Copper Oxides (REBCO), including elements such as yttrium, gadolinium, europium, and samarium, are particularly notable. A key phase in these materials is the REBa₂Cu₃O_{7-δ} (RE-123) phase, which exhibits superconductivity [5–8]. The versatility of REBCO materials allows them to be adapted into various forms, each tailored to harness specific superconducting properties [9–13].

From Yttrium Barium Copper Oxide (YBCO), a key member of the REBCO family, single-domain superconducting bulks are produced. These bulks, integral in applications ranging from magnetic levitation in maglev trains to energy storage systems, are useful thanks to their capacity to trap magnetic fields and facilitate self-stabilizing magnetic levitation through quantum locking [3,14–16]. The production of these single-domain bulks commonly employs methods such as Top-seeded Melt Growth (TSMG) and Top-seeded Infiltration Growth (TSIG), each with their own specific set of benefits and drawbacks [17–22].

In industrial applications, one of the primary properties of the single-domain YBCO bulks is maximal levitation force, a critical parameter dictating their suitability across various grades of applications [23–26]. Despite their irreplaceable properties, the production of REBCO bulk superconductors is not without challenges [27]. The intricate manufacturing processes often lead to defects such as secondary grains or large cracks, especially in larger bulks, culminating in a significant volume of material wastage [22,28]. Furthermore, other types of REBCO superconductors such as thin-film superconducting tapes also produce REBCO waste during their manufacturing processes [29,30]. And even existing REBCO products at the end of their lives contribute to growing amount of this waste, possessing a high potential on the one hand, but representing a hazardous matter on the other hand (due to the presence of heavy metals). Addressing this issue, our previous work introduced a novel recycling method, demonstrating the feasibility of reusing all YBCO (and subsequently all REBCO) waste in producing recycled bulks, thereby solving this environmental issue [31].

The current study builds upon this foundation, aiming to explore how varying proportions of recycled YBCO material affect the microstructure and properties of second-generation single-domain bulks. By analyzing these variations, we aim to establish a correlation between the

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Fig. 1. A scheme showing which analysis methods were used for the respective forms of sample (recycled precursor powder – single-domain bulk – polished bulk microstructure/crushed bulk).

Fig. 2. Temperature profile of the precursors' calcinations and subsequent crystal growth.

recycled material content and the resulting superconducting properties. This insight is crucial for tailoring the recycled material content in industrial precursors to achieve desired properties for specific applications, thus contributing to a new era of sustainable and efficient production of REBCO superconductors.

2. Experimental

In this work, the following chemicals were used: nitric acid 65 % (p. a., Penta), potassium hydroxide (p. a., 85 %, Penta), sulfuric acid 96 % (p. a., Penta), $C_2H_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ (p. a., 99 %, Penta), $NH_4OH < 23$ % (p. a., Penta), copper(II) oxide (p. a., Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic), barium carbonate (99 %+, Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic), yttrium(III) oxide (99.99 %, Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic), cerium(IV) oxide (99.9 %, Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic). The processed YBCO waste was obtained from industrial manufacturer CAN Superconductors.

Samples were analyzed by laser diffraction (LD), atomic emission spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma (ICP-OES), X-ray diffraction (XRD), optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron mi-

croscopy (SEM) using 10 kV acceleration voltage. For levitation force measurement, we used an in-house setup. The used apparatus comprised of a PT4000–50 kg load cell characterized by its ± 0.1 N accuracy, coupled with a 24-bit ADC Data Acquisition system and a NdFeB permanent magnet (N52, measuring 25 mm in diameter and height, and producing a magnetic field of 0.575 T). The samples were cooled below critical temperature without exposure to an external magnetic field. The data were obtained across a range from 2 mm to 30 mm above the bulk, at 77 K temperature. Trapped field maps were produced by an in-house designed device based on a Hall probe scanning the samples. The data were obtained at a 1 mm distance from the surface. The samples were cooled in an external magnetic field of about 1 T. The relationship between distance from the bulk (d) and levitation force (F) can be expressed with the following exponential function: $F = F_{max} + A \exp(Bd)$, where A and B are parameters. This function is commonly used to extrapolate maximal levitation force (F_{max}) at the surface of the bulk [32].

Different analysis methods were used in each step of sample manufacturing. The corresponding methods for each step can be seen in Fig. 1. Recycled precursor powders were analyzed with LD, ICP-OES and XRD. After the TSMG growth, the prepared single-domain bulks were analyzed using levitation force measurement and with trapped field mapping. The bulks were then cut in half perpendicularly to the square-shaped main grain. One of the halves was crushed and analyzed with XRD and ICP-OES. The surface of the other halves cut was polished and analyzed with OM and SEM.

The recycled REBCO material was produced from defective REBCO bulks from industrial production. The complete recycling technique used, along with all associated analytics can be found in our previous publication [31].

1. Defective YBCO bulks were ground into a fine powder using a disc mill
2. The powdered waste was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid, a highly exothermic process requiring slow addition of waste and constant stirring. The reaction resulted in a solution containing Ba^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Y^{3+} , and NO_3^- ions, with some precipitated $Ba(NO_3)_2$ due to its limited solubility.
3. The mixture was diluted with a large amount of distilled water until all remaining solid $Ba(NO_3)_2$ was fully dissolved.

Fig. 3. Particle size of the recycled precursor with industrial precursor as reference.

Table 1

Cumulative particle size value for the first and last decile and median.

Sample name	$D_x 10$ (μm)	$D_x 50$ (μm)	$D_x 90$ (μm)
REF ground	5.5	12.5	26.1
15 % ground	6.0	11.9	23.7
30 % ground	5.1	10.6	20.8
45 % ground	4.5	9.4	19.2

- Ammonium hydroxide was added to raise the solution's pH of approximately 8 to 9 to increase the yield of subsequent precipitation.
- If the processed waste contains silver (common in other REBCO systems), it is dissolved alongside other elements. Subsequently, the selective precipitation of Ag^+ from the solution was achieved by the addition of HCl. The obtained AgCl is purified, filtered and reduced to metallic silver or Ag_2O for reuse.
- Oxalic acid was added to the solution to precipitate yttrium, copper, and barium ions as their respective oxalates or oxalate hydrates.
- To increase the recovery of barium, a second precipitation step was performed by adding ammonium hydroxide to the filtrate. This produced additional $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, which was filtered and combined with the initial precipitate.
- The collected precipitates were thoroughly washed with demineralized water to remove impurities, dried, and analyzed for their chemical composition.
- Any remaining toxic Ba^{2+} ions in the filtrate were removed by converting them into insoluble BaSO_4 using sulfuric acid.
- The process previously demonstrated an overall yield of 71 % by weight, recovering most of the Y-Ba-Cu elements. Losses were primarily attributed to the relatively high solubility of barium oxalate.

- The obtained dry precipitate was analyzed by ICP. The precipitate was mixed with small amounts of raw materials (BaCO_3 and CuO) to achieve the desired stoichiometry and with a large amount of raw materials (BaCO_3 , CuO and Y_2O_3) to obtain precursor powders containing 15 %, 30 %, and 45 % by weight.
- The prepared precursor powders underwent repeated calcinations with intermediate homogenization, producing a batches of precursor powders with varying amount of recycled material.

Recycled single-domain YBCO bulks were prepared through a modified industrial process, using precursor powders described above with the following stoichiometry: $1.0 \text{ YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_x \cdot 0.4 \text{ Y}_2\text{BaCuO}_x$ (Y-123: Y-211 = 1.0: 0.4) [31]. CeO_2 (0.5 wt.%) was also added to achieve better Y-211 particle distribution during TSMG. Three batches of powder precursor (each weighing about 1.2 kg) with 15 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 45 wt.% of the recycled material were prepared. These were then processed in an identical series of steps as a normal industrial precursor would. The precursors were calcined in four steps between 850 °C and 880 °C with 10 °C increments and between each step the precursors were homogenized by grinding. Cylindrical pellets (32 mm diameter, 42 g) were uniaxially pressed from the calcined precursors with circa 50 MPa of pressure. Through TSMG (top-seeded melt growth) method (commercial Nd-123 seeds, air atmosphere) single-domain crystals were produced from the precursors. The following temperature profile was used: heating to 900 °C in 3 h, heating to 930 °C in 1 h, heating to 1065 °C in 1 h, holding at 1065 °C for 1 h, cooling to 1010 °C in 15 min, cooling to 995 °C in 30 min, cooling to 991 °C in 1 h, crystal growth at a temperature of 991 °C for 30 h, cooling to a temperature of 987 °C in 2 h. The used temperature profile can be seen in Fig. 2 together with temperature profiles of the previous calcinations.

Subsequently, all produced bulks (10 bulks per composition, a total of 30 bulks; grown in 6 batches of 5 pieces) were annealed in a dynamic atmosphere of pure oxygen between 300 °C and 450 °C for 200 h to

Fig. 4. Comparison of XRD data of the recycled precursors with varying content of recycled material with industrial precursor as reference.

Table 2

Comparison of stoichiometry of Y: Ba: Cu in the recycled precursors calculated from ICP-OES data. Target growth stoichiometry is mentioned as a reference.

	Growth stoichiometry	15 %	30 %	45 %
Y	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80
Ba	2.40	2.46	2.45	2.43
Cu	3.40	3.50	3.45	3.41

saturate the crystal lattice with oxygen. The last step was machining of the bulks to 10 mm height and 28 mm diameter. For more detailed information on the recycling process, please refer to our earlier publication [31].

3. Results and discussion

During and after the production of the YBCO bulks with recycled content (recycling technique summarized in the experimental section; see our previous publication for more details regarding the process

Fig. 5. Maximal levitation force of recycled samples.

Table 3
Overview table of chosen samples' names and descriptions.

Sample name	F_{max} (N)	Description
YBCO-REF	79.2 ± 2.0	From production, selected as a reference
YBCO-15 %-AVG	76.6 ± 2.0	Sample with F_{max} close to the calculated average from a batch containing 15 wt.% of recycled material
YBCO-30 %-AVG	72.2 ± 2.0	Sample with F_{max} close to the calculated average from a batch containing 30 wt.% of recycled material
YBCO-45 %-AVG	60.5 ± 2.0	Sample with F_{max} close to the calculated average from a batch containing 45 wt.% of recycled material
YBCO-82 N	82.4 ± 2.0	Sample with highest F_{max} from the batch containing 15 wt.% of recycled material
YBCO-55 N	54.9 ± 2.0	Sample with lowest F_{max} from the batch containing 45 wt.% of recycled material

Fig. 6. Maps of the trapped field of selected bulks.

Fig. 7. Maxima of trapped fields of all bulks.

[31]), several analyses were performed to see how the recycled bulks compare with their counterparts made from raw materials. To follow the process and analyses more easily, see Fig. 1. In the first step, the recycled precursor powders were analyzed by LD together with an industrial precursor to compare their respective particle size distributions. The powders were analyzed before final grinding in a disc mill as well as after this final grinding step. The grinding times for each sample were identical (4 mins). Data before final grinding can be found in Supporting information (Figure S11 and Table S11) for this article. Particle size distributions of the ground samples are shown in Fig. 3 along with the selected quantiles displayed in Table 1. A clear trend can be seen in median particle size of the ground samples: the higher the recycled content, the smaller the median particle size. While D_{x50} for the reference sample was 12.5 μm , for the sample with 45 % of recycled material D_{x50} was 9.4 μm . This is most likely caused by smaller particles in the recycled material, which was prepared by precipitation. This difference is relatively small and did not appear to influence crystal growth in a noticeable manner.

In the next step, XRD of the precursors was also measured to determine phase composition in order to prove whether the content of recycled material would influence the phase composition of the recycled precursors. The analysis (see Fig. 4) showed the presence of phases $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ (Y-123, ICDD 01-078-2274) and Y_2BaCuO_5 (Y-211, ICDD 01-080-0770) in all precursors (recycled as well as the reference precursors) [33,34]. The XRD analysis did not reveal any differences between the recycled powders and reference powder. No other impurities (other crystalline phases) were detected.

ICP-OES analysis was also performed to determine the precise elemental composition of the recycled precursors. From the obtained data, the stoichiometry of Y: Ba: Cu was calculated and normalized to $Y = 1.8$ so that it could be easily compared with used bulk growth stoichiometry ($Y-123: Y-211 = 1: 0.4$ gives overall yttrium stoichiometry of 1.8 for theoretical stoichiometry $\text{Y}_{1.8}\text{Ba}_{2.4}\text{Cu}_{3.4}\text{O}_x$, see Table 2). Based on the data, it seems that the recycled precursor powders exhibit a slight yttrium deficiency. This deviation from the target (growth) stoichiometry is a sum of inaccuracies such as the composition measurement inaccuracy of the recycled material, the inaccuracy of weighing the raw materials used to prepare the recycled precursors and the inaccuracy of the composition measurement of the recycled precursors. The highest deviation from the target growth stoichiometry is in the 15 % recycled precursor. However, as will be later revealed, bulks from this precursor achieved the best superconducting properties, therefore the deviation in the composition did not have a large negative effect on the recycled

Fig. 8. Microstructure analysis of the selected bulks using OM. Borders of the main grain are highlighted in red lines, blue line in the YBCO 55 N sample indicates a crack. Blue dashed lines mark areas analyzed by SEM.

bulks. Nonetheless, the issue of recycled precursor composition is one of the areas, where this recycling method can be still improved in the future. This could be done through working in greater quantities, which is achievable in industrial settings.

After detailed characterization of the recycled precursors, single-domain bulks were produced from the precursors through the TSMG method. They were subsequently annealed in pure O_2 atmosphere to saturate the lattice with oxygen and turn non-superconducting

Fig. 9. Microstructure analysis of bulks' areas directly below seed. Six SEM images were joint together for each sample. The rectangle marked areas are analyzed in greater resolution in the next step.

tetragonal Y-123 (space group $P4/mmm$) to superconducting orthorhombic Y-123 (space group $Pmmm$) [35]. After annealing, the bulks were machined to diameter of 28 mm and height of 10 mm. Their microstructure and superconducting properties were then characterized in detail. For some of these analyses, the bulks needed to be cut in half, where one half of the bulk was polished and analyzed with OM and SEM, while the other half was crushed and analyzed with ICP-OES and XRD. To easily follow all this process, see Fig. 1.

Levitation force of all produced bulks was measured. The levitation

force maxima of all bulks can be seen in Fig. 5. Average maximal forces for each batch (15 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 45 wt.% of recycled material) were calculated. The highest and the lowest performing bulks from each batch were eliminated from average force calculation as data outliers. The average maximal levitation force for 15 % added recycled material is $F_{\max} = 76.7$ N, for 30 % $F_{\max} = 72.1$ N and for 45 % $F_{\max} = 64.0$ N. For context, the highest-grade bulks from industrial production have maximal levitation force above 80 N.

Based on the calculated maximal levitation forces, there appears to

Fig. 10. Microstructure analysis of bulks ranging from macro defects resolution (bubbles etc.) to resolution that allows to distinguish between Y-123 matrix and inclusions.

Fig. 11. EDS line scans identifying Y-123 matrix and inclusions.

be a relationship between the amount of recycled material used and the average maximal levitation force. Specifically, as the percentage of recycled material increases, the average maximal levitation force tends to decrease. For bulks classified as Grade A, the levitation force exceeds

80 N; for Grade B, it falls between 60 N and 80 N; bulks below 60 N are discarded.

After trapped field mapping, all samples were cut in half and analyzed as seen from Scheme in Fig. 1. The samples chosen for detailed

Fig. 12. Sub-section of YBCO phase diagram with compositions of the recycled bulks and of YBCO-REF marked. Two sets of compositions were calculated: first from ICP-OES data and second by Rietveld analysis from obtained XRD data.

microstructural analysis were the overall best performing bulk, the overall worst performing one and bulks that were closest to average F_{\max} value for each batch (15 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 45 wt.%). As a reference, bulk from industrial production with F_{\max} value close to industrial average was analyzed together with them. The selected samples are summarized in Table 3.

Subsequently, trapped field mapping of all produced bulks was performed. Trapped field maps of the selected bulks can be seen in Fig. 6. The trapped field maps of the remaining bulks can be found in the Supporting information (Figure SI2, SI3 and SI4). The maxima of trapped fields of all bulks can be seen in Fig. 7. The average maximal trapped field value for each batch (15 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 45 wt.% of recycled material) was calculated. The highest and the lowest performing bulks from each batch were eliminated from the calculation as data outliers. The average maximal trapped field for 15 % added recycled material is $B_{\text{trp max}} = 0.45$ T, for 30 % $B_{\text{trp max}} = 0.39$ T and for 45 % $B_{\text{trp max}} = 0.32$ T. Trapped field mapping of a YBCO bulk, however, mainly serves to indirectly identify structural defects such as macro cracks or secondary grains. These defects match with areas of low trapped field. A smaller crack can be seen in YBCO-30 %-AVG and a larger crack in YBCO-55N. In accordance with previous findings, there is not a strict correlation between F_{\max} and a respective maximum of trapped field within the same sample. This is because the trapped field is not the only parameter influencing F_{\max} of a given bulk. The best correlation factor for F_{\max} is the size of the main grain in combination with the quality of its microstructure. This explains how the YBCO-82 N sample can have higher F_{\max} than samples YBCO-REF and YBCO-15 %-AVG while having a lower maximum of trapped field.

After the measurement of superconducting properties, selected samples were cut in half, polished and their microstructure was analyzed by OM and SEM. The micrographs of the bulks can be seen in Fig. 8. From the micrographs, the boundaries of the main grains can be determined. These are highlighted with red lines. In terms of the overall microstructure quality (number and size of macro defects, such as bubbles and horizontal cracks), there is no significant difference between the bulks, except for the YBCO-55 N sample, which contains a large crack highlighted by a blue line. This was further confirmed by trapped field mapping data in Fig. 6 (a large area of about one-fourth of

the bulk surface that has a very low trapped field).

Blue dashed lines in Fig. 8 mark areas under crystal seed that were analyzed with SEM. This cross-section analysis, although more detailed than the OM photos, did not reveal any irregularities in the microstructure quality of the recycled bulks in comparison to the reference. The SEM cross-sections can be seen in Fig. 9. In Fig. 10, sequences of SEM micrographs with increasing magnifications can be seen. These range from macro defects resolution (bubbles and cracks) to high-resolution micrographs that allow one to distinguish between the dark grey matrix and the lighter inclusions. With EDS line scans, it was possible to identify the dark grey matrix as the Y-123 phase. The slightly lighter inclusions were identified as the Y-211 phase, and the lightest inclusions were identified as BaCeO_3 . In Figure SI5 an EDS point spectrum proving the presence of BaCeO_3 can be seen. The line scans can be seen in Fig. 11. Both types of inclusions were expected, and their size and shape did not differ significantly between the reference sample and the recycled samples. The purpose of Y-211 inclusions in YBCO bulks is to serve as a non-superconducting pinning phase. A pinning phase allows a sample to reach higher critical current (thus reaching both higher maximum levitation force and higher trapped field). In YBCO bulks, the particle size and dispersion of Y-211 phase pinning influences the overall critical current (it is desirable to have small particle size and homogenous distribution). CeO_2 is commonly added in small amounts to YBCO bulk precursors because it causes decomposition of the Y-211 phase during TSMG, forming BaCeO_3 and Y_2O_3 [36–38].

The crushed halves of the selected bulks were analyzed with ICP-OES to determine precise elemental composition after growth. The composition of the YBCO-REF sample falls above the Y-123 and Y-211 binary equilibrium in the phase diagram (Fig. 12), suggesting the presence of trace amounts of BaCuO_2 together with Y-123 and Y-211. On the other hand, the recycled samples all fall under the Y-123 and Y-211 binary equilibrium, suggesting the presence of CuO. There are several possible contributing factors to this difference. As mentioned before, the composition of the recycled precursors did not exactly match the desired growth stoichiometry. However, the main factor influencing the overall sample composition is the composition shift that happens during the melting and recrystallization of the sample during TSMG and the subsequent machining of the bulk.

Fig. 13. XRD data and Rietveld fits of the recycled and reference bulks.

Table 4

Comparison of Y-123 and Y-211 content in the recycled and reference bulks calculated by Rietveld analysis from XRD data.

	YBCO-REF	YBCO-15 %-AVG	YBCO-30 %-AVG	YBCO-45 %-AVG
Y-123 (wt. %)	74.11	71.89	72.05	70.33
Y-211 (wt. %)	25.89	28.11	27.95	29.67

XRD data of these samples were also obtained in order to perform Rietveld analysis on that data. In Fig. 13, the experimental data together with the calculated diffraction patterns can be seen. From this analysis, the phase composition of each sample was determined to see their Y-123 and Y-211 content (see Table 4). CuO and BaCuO₂, whose presence was suggested by ICP-OES, were not detected by XRD. In Fig. 12, a subsection of the YBCO phase diagram with marked compositions of the analyzed bulks can be seen. Both ICP-OES and data obtained by Rietveld refinement are visualized.

4. Conclusions

The findings of this study demonstrate a promising approach to recycling REBCO materials, particularly in producing single-domain YBCO bulks from recycled precursors. Building on our previously developed recycling method, the successful growth of bulks containing up to 45 % precursor with only a slight decrease in relevant properties demonstrates its significant potential. The effectiveness of this method in recycling single-domain bulk waste followed by TSMG growth suggests that it could be broadly applicable for recycling various forms of REBCO waste materials. Furthermore, given that the properties of the final bulks appear to be a function of the amount of recycled material, the amount of recycled material in recycled precursor can be optimized based on the desired properties of the final product. For example, recycled YBCO bulks with a levitation force in the range of 70 to 80 N, reliably achievable with up to 30 wt.% recycled material, remain suitable for standard applications like high-speed bearings. Some of these bulks even achieve values of maximal levitation force exceeding 80 N and can therefore be used in the highest grade of applications. One of the key challenges identified is the control over the stoichiometry of the recycled precursor, which impacts the melt-growth process (unless tuned specifically for bulks from recycled material) and therefore directly influences the quality of final bulks. While the deviation from

the target growth stoichiometry did not pose a significant challenge, further optimization of precursor preparation is necessary, as it will allow to either improve the superconducting properties of the recycled bulks or increase the amount of recycled powder consumed. This could be achieved by scaling up the process to industrial quantities, where homogeneity and stoichiometry are typically easier to maintain. This potentially allows the waste produced by high-demand applications to be consumed in large quantities by other products, improving both environmental sustainability and economic efficiency of REBCO production. With further refinement and scaling, this approach has the potential to significantly reduce the sustainability and cost of producing REBCO materials for various high-tech applications.

Data statement

According to the open science principles, raw data can be found at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10906954.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Sklenka: Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Ondřej Jančovič:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Tomáš Hlášek:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michal Lojka:** Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **David Sedmidubský:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Filip Antončík:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.oceram.2025.100749.

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